

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Yoqubjonova Habiba Yoqubjon qizi

KIYINISH MADANIYATI INSONING DIDI QANDAY EKANINI KO'RSATADI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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